

Discourses on Women: Role of Social Institutions in Sue Monk Kidd's *The Invention of Wings*

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Abstract

Discourse forms the belief systems, cultural performances, and the social rules and norms of a society. It transmits knowledge which affects the views of people and also the way in which social institutions work in a society. This study examines the relationship between power and knowledge and the effect of various knowledge discourses on women. Sue Monk Kidd's historical novel *The Invention of Wings* (2014) depicts the effect of various knowledge discourses on power relations on the women. Thus, the study is interconnected with the theory of power and knowledge by Michel Foucault and the effect they have on Kidd's female characters. The two main female characters and also the narrators of the novel, Sarah Grimké and Hetty "Handful," are exposed to different discourses of power by the social institutions in their society. The women in the novel attempt to challenge these discourses and their effect on their lives by using different resistance mechanisms.

Keywords: Gender, Discourse, Feminism, Power and Knowledge, Resistance

Introduction

Discourse refers to ways in which knowledge is organized in a society in a way that it structures social relations by institutionalizing a particular way of thinking while undermining others. It influences how ideas are put into practice and how those ideas regulate the conduct of the society, as Stuart Hall defines in "The West and the Rest:" "All social practices entail meaning and meaning shapes and influences what we do---all the practices that we have possess a discursive aspect to them" (291). Discourse creates subject positions, and turns people into controllable objects. In *The Archaeology of Knowledge*, Michel Foucault examines the power of discourse in society: "Discourse is not the majestically unfolding manifestation of a thinking, knowing, speaking subject, but, on the contrary, a totality in which dispersion of the subject and his discontinuity with himself may be determined" (54). Foucault argues that in a society, the social interactions of individuals are controlled through a system of power and knowledge relations, which also dictates their perception of themselves. According to Foucault "Power is not an institution, and not a structure; neither is it a certain strength we are endowed with; it is the name that one attributes to a complex strategical situation in a particular society" (*The History of Sexuality*, 93). Power is not something that is physically enforced on people rather it is a result of the relations between individuals and society. In *The Subject of Power*, Foucault states, "the exercise of power is not violence, nor consent, but a total structure of actions brought to bear upon possible actions it incites, it induces, it seduces, it makes easier or more

difficult; in the extreme it constrains or forbids absolutely; it is nevertheless always a way of acting upon an acting subject or acting subjects by virtue of their acting or being capable of action” (789). Foucault's theories suggest that discourses in society play a significant role in determining how women are perceived in society. These discourses are formed by power dynamics that uphold the gender hierarchies in society and restrict the scope for women's agency and empowerment. Foucault's theories have had a big impact on feminist theory, and they have been applied to examine how power dynamics affect sexuality, gender identity, and social norms.

In Sue Monk Kidd's novel *The Invention of Wings* (2014), women face dominant power relations and discourses, which affect their self-perception. Aspects as the education level, career choices, and the standards of womanhood are affected because of the power discourses existing in the society. Kidd's novel is a fictional account of the lives of two sisters who existed in South Carolina, America in the nineteenth century, Sarah Moore Grimké and Angelina Grimké. They were among the first women to take part in the abolition movement in America and were also the early leaders in the women's rights movement. Sarah was also widely known as the mother of the women's suffrage movement. Kidd has also included the account of Handful aka Hetty too in her novel, who was a slave in the Grimké house. Kidd decided to write the fictional account of these women's lives as she was captivated by their story, and the sacrifices they did for their causes (*The Oprah Magazine*, 90-94). These women, though oppressed by the social constructs around them, set out on their own paths and show enough courage to raise their voice.

Power Discourses in *The Invention of Wings*

The Invention of Wings begins with the account of Sarah Grimké's eleventh birthday where she is gifted a ten-year-old slave Hetty “Handful” as a birthday present. Though Sarah is young, she despises slavery and refuses to take a slave as a gift. Despite her refusing to accept this gift, she has to take Handful as her slave. The novel then follows the journey of this duo, a slave and the daughter of the Grimké household that owns her, over the time period of thirty-five years. The female characters in Kidd's novel are affected by several discourses in the society. The novel is set in the nineteenth century Charleston, South Carolina, when the ideas of the equality of gender and race were considered radical.

Sarah is educated at home unlike her brothers, who received a conventional education. Amigot and Pujal state “discourses of women's nature and disciplining and normalizing practices are especially relevant with regard to the production of “proper” feminine bodies and subjectivities” (650-651). Sarah is taught by a home tutor, Madame Ruffin, whom she despises, “I despised her, and her 'polite education for the female mind,' which was composed of needlework, manners, drawing, basic reading, penmanship, piano, Bible, French, and enough arithmetic to add two and two” (22). She was aware of the inferiority of her education as compared to her

brothers'. Sarah is not allowed to receive a true education only because she is a girl, she wishes to be someone in life and wants to know things, but being a daughter instead of a son doesn't allow her to do so, "Oh, to be a son! I adored Father because he treated me almost as if I *were* a son" (22). Sarah's wish to be a "son" in order to feel important aptly describes the inequality of gender that exists in her society. Sarah's father is an attorney and judge at South Carolina, Sarah loves to read books from her father's library. She is very good at debates, in a discussion with her father and brothers, Sarah is awed by her father's reaction, "Father slapped his hand on the table. 'If Sarah was a boy, she would be the greatest jurist in South Caroline.'" (24)." Because of the gender discourses existing in the society, Sarah's wish to study law or to be a jurist cannot be fulfilled only because she is a woman.

Foucault's view is that power is a product of the individuals' interaction and is deeply rooted in the social relations of society (*The Subject and Power*, 792). Sarah lives in a society where the experiences and self-worth of women are constructed by power relations, Handful remarks on Sarah, "My body might be a slave, but not my mind. For you, it's the other way round" (231). Handful knows that Sarah is trapped same as her but she was trapped by her own mind and by the minds of the society. Foucault asserts in the essay "The Subject and Power" that power is a product of interaction between the individuals in a society and is ingrained in the layers of the social relations (792). Sarah's mind is a slave of the prevailing beliefs existing in her culture, religion, and her society. Sarah's wish to be a jurist is shattered only because it is considered "unwomanly" in the society she lives in, "For a woman to aspire to be a lawyer – well, possibly, the world would end" (24). Sarah is restricted by the limits that are imposed on the females in her society. Sarah's father is well aware of her capabilities and considers her smarter than her brothers, he states when he is near his death, "You were smarter than even Thomas or John, but you're female, another cruelty I was helpless to change" (208). Yet, because of the existing social norms, her father loathes Sarah's wish to be a jurist, and considers it a shameful act, "... You shame yourself. You shame us all. Where did you ever get the notion that you could study law?" (89).

Handful is an urban slave who yearns to live freely, away from the walls of the Grimké household. She sometimes tries to challenge the system of slavery but suffers badly because of that. Kidd has described a black girl who is destined to be a slave along with a white girl who owns her, yet both of them strive for freedom of different kinds. Handful being a slave, longs for the freedom of the body; Sarah although being a white woman is limited by her role as a daughter to the Grimké family, her father remarks, "...we Grimkés do not subvert the institutions and laws by which we live, even if we don't agree with them" (76). When Sarah tries to teach Handful a few alphabets, her books are taken from her, and she is denied access to the books from the library, "...so soon after my books being taken away, quite soured me on the female life" (86).

The women are expected to give up their goals and ambitions for the sake of the family and society, Sarah's anti-slavery ideas and her wish to be a jurist are

discouraged, and she is told to go husband hunting instead, “How highborn and moneyed this husband would turn out to be would depend entirely on the allure of my face, the delicacy of my physique, the skill of my seamstress, and the charisma of my tête-à-tête” (97). Although Sarah's mother discourages her radical ideas, but she seems to have faced the same when she was young which becomes clear when she remarks, “Every girl comes into the world with varying degrees of ambition, even if it's only the hope of not belonging body and soul to her husband. I was a girl once, believe it or not (90).” Even when Sarah goes North and gets involved in the Quaker ministry along with her sister Nina, they are appreciated as long as they do not state their own views, “As long as we talk about being good helpmates to our husbands, it's well and good...but the moment we veer into social matters, or God forbid, politics, they want to silence us like children” (325). Even after joining the Quaker ministry, Sarah for a moment gets self-doubt, “What I feared was the immensity of it all – a female abolition agent traveling the country with a national mandate. I wanted to say, *Who am I to do this, a woman?* But that voice was not mine. It was Father's voice. It was Thomas'...” (366). On the other hand, Charlotte, who is Handful's mother, and has been a slave in the Grimké household since years, longs for freedom for herself and Handful. She is the main seamstress in the Grimké family, when she is not working on her quilts; she works secretly outside to save money in order to buy freedom. She wants her daughter to know their own worth apart from being slaves.

Resistance against Power Discourses by Women

“If you must err, do so on the side of audacity” (9), this little slogan devised by Sarah reflects her courage to resist the societal norms existing in her society. Foucault asserts, “Where there is power, there is always the possibility of resistance” (*Discipline and Punish*, 142), the acts of resistance by female characters in *The Invention of Wings* can be seen in several instances. According to Amigot and Pujal, “Resistances are immanent in relations of power; whether or not these resistances transform a situation will depend on their articulation and proliferation” (662-663). Sarah displays a strong sense of equality and social justice; although she is only eleven years old, she despises slavery, and her refusal to accept a slave as a birthday present marks the beginning of the signs of resistance shown by her. Sarah teaches Handful to read and write a few alphabets, despite her knowledge that her family would never approve of this. She faces the fury of her father, and is banned to enter the library. After she is fiercely mocked and insulted for her “shameful” act of wishing to be a jurist, Sarah expresses her wish to be the godmother to her newly born sister, Angelina. This was her own little act of resistance; though she was not able to go against the wishes of her family, she wanted to mold her sister in her own image and make her the purpose of her life, “From the days Nina was in her crib, I'd proselytized her about the evils of slavery” (99). Nina refuses to take a slave as a present on her eleventh birthday, and Sarah succeeds in a way as this time her mother had to give in, “...Nina had refused her human present with such vehemence, Mother had given up

out of sheer weariness” (179). Nina became the voice of Sarah's radical ideas. Sarah's life takes a turnabout when she goes North when her father is ill, she does not come back right after her father's death as she enjoyed the freedom she experienced away from her home. When Sarah is introduced to the Quaker faith by Israel Morris, and finds out that they have female ministers too, she has the urge to go north again, and she wishes to be a minister there. Though she is blocked by her own mind, “unmarried daughters didn't go off to live unprotected on their own in a foreign place...they didn't throw over their lives and their reputations and their family name. They didn't create scandals” (241). Her decision of leaving home for north is not only an act of resistance against the existing discourses and dominant power relations in her society, but also a resistance against her own captive mind. Angelina, on the other hand, causes scandalous rebellions by speaking out against slavery in the Presbyterian Church in Charleston, and later joins her sister in the North as Quaker. Angelina is more outspoken and headstrong than Sarah, she shares the passion of Sarah against slavery. The two sisters set out on their paths to abolition and the women's movement together. Although Sarah is introduced to the ministry by Israel Morris, he assumes that Sarah's ambition is only a response to her failure to be a part of his life. Sarah turns down the marriage proposal of Israel because he expected her to leave ministry after she is married, “I hadn't imagined you would want to continue with your ambition after we married” (329). Sarah well understood that she cannot have him and her ambition both, and she decides to choose her ambition. In one of the letters to her sister, she states, “How could I choose someone who would force me to give up my own small reach for meaning? I chose myself, and without consolation” (336). Sarah resists against the societal norms expecting women to get married and become good homemakers by instead deciding to dedicate her life to advocacy and activism, and asserts her own independence and agency. Even when the two sisters become part of the abolition movement, they are dominated because of their gender, when Angelina's letter is published in a notorious anti-slavery paper, the response of the ministry was unwelcoming, “Matters like this – they aren't the work of a woman's life” (356), and are told to confine their audiences to only women. When they talk of women's reform, it is seen as a distraction and parting away from abolition, “...these good men who wished to quash us, gently, of course, benignly, for the good of abolition, for our own good, for their good, for the greater good. It was all so familiar. Theirs was only a different kind of muzzle” (382). Sarah and Angelina do not agree to these terms and very confidently refuse to “turn their backs” on themselves and on “their own sex” (382). It did not seem fair to campaign for the slaves' rights while ignoring their own, “Whatsoever it is morally right for a man to do, it is morally right for a woman to do. She is clothed by her Maker with the same rights, the same duties” (383). Later Sarah helps Handful to be free from the confines of Grimké household, and her transformation from a little girl who used to stammer to a strong woman who did not hesitate to state her word is well noticed by Handful, “This ain't the same Sarah who left here. She had a firm look in her eye and her voice didn't dither or hesitate like it

used to. She'd been boiled down to a good, strong broth” (406).

Handful faced both the jeopardy of being a woman as well as a slave. Yet she rebels against the societal norms and discourses in her own ways and refuses to be submissive to the society she lives in and stands up for her own beliefs. Handful is taught by Sarah to read and she uses this ability to gain knowledge. She practices to write in the dirt and steals books to read, even though the slaves are strictly forbidden to get educated. Her very first instance of rebellion was her taking bath in her “owner's” copper bathtub, to which Sarah remarks, “She had the look of someone who had declared herself...” (129). Handful challenges the limitations placed upon her because of her gender as well as race, and fights for her freedom and rights. Handful has learned to be tough and shrewd from her mother, Charlotte aka Mauma, “If mauma can do it, I can do it. I'll do it lame, blind, and backward, if I have to” (197). Charlotte constantly keeps fighting for the freedom for herself and her daughter, Handful has been instilled these qualities by her. Charlotte is the head seamstress in the house of Grimké's, and she uses her skill to assert agency and autonomy in her life. Though she is a slave but maintains her self-respect and dignity till her last breath, she says to Handful, “Don't you remember me for that. Don't you remember I'm a slave and work hard. When you think of me, you say, she never did belong to those people. She never belong to nobody but herself” (348). After her mother's demise, Handful takes the position of the head-seamstress for Grimké's and begins acting on the rebellious tendencies. She makes the plan to escape from Charleston, and to gain freedom for herself and her half-sister sister, Sky. The rebellion of female characters in the novel against the discourses existing in their society highlights the oppressive and unjust nature of the power systems.

Conclusion

Discourses are thought and knowledge systems that are formed and perpetuated by social institutions and power structures. Discourses influence how we perceive the world and how we fit into it, and how people in authoritative positions use them to manipulate both the individuals and the society at large. Discourses on women are the ways in which language, ideas, and cultural practices construct and shape the understanding of women's roles, identities, and experiences. They have significant effects on their lives, even shaping their opportunities, relationships, and self-perception. The examination of the novel *The Invention of Wings* in the light of Foucault's concept of discourse, and the theory of power and knowledge, illuminates several power discourses operating through gender and racial hierarchies in the society which constrain women's rights from all aspects. Foucault's theory of power and knowledge provides a useful framework for understanding how power operates in the society and how it can be resisted and challenged. Sarah Grimké is denied formal education because of her gender, though she is highly intelligent and has an insatiable desire for knowledge. She is expected instead to adhere to particular societal norms and expectations as a woman, and is supposed to get married, have kids, and live her

life doing housework. Sarah surmounts these social barriers, and becomes an abolitionist for the rights of slaves, which is against the prevalent norms of the society casting women in a subordinate position to men. Sarah, while preaching abolition to people, along with her sister, Angelina, becomes more aware of her own limitations as a woman, and the struggle to end slavery also becomes a movement for women's equality. Handful, on the other hand, faces cruel treatment, as being both a slave and a woman. To resist her enslavement, she defies her master, but she is ultimately punished for her actions. She finds empowerment through her mother, Charlotte, who constantly stands up to the oppressive forces of slavery and refuses to be reduced to an object of ownership and exploitation. She provides Handful with an identity and self-awareness that helps to transcend her enslavement. This paper shows how discourses create gender and racial hierarchies supporting the positions of dominant groups. Women like Sarah are denied an education and pressured to adhere to gender norms, while Handful and other slaves are exposed to abuse and exploitation. The dominant discourse, which portrays gender inequality and slavery as natural and inevitable, is reflective of these power dynamics. However, the stories of Sarah, Handful and other women in the novel also demonstrate how power can be resisted and challenged.

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